

EnergyMeasures

Tailored measures supporting energy vulnerable households

D6.4

Project Website

 <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

 [@NRGMeasures](https://twitter.com/NRGMeasures)

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About EnergyMeasures

EnergyMEASURES is working to address energy poverty in seven European countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland and the United Kingdom. The project comprises two complementary and synergistic strands of work.

The first strand involves working with energy poor households to improve their energy efficiency through a combination of low-cost measures, and changes in energy-related behaviours and practices. Recruited householders will be provided with low-cost energy measures and empowered to change their energy-related behaviours and practices through an approach that takes account of existing housing conditions and is reflective of their lived experience.

The second strand comprises working with municipalities, energy authorities, housing associations and other relevant actors to assess how current multi-level institutional contexts affect efforts to alleviate energy vulnerability in the participating countries. This knowledge will be used to develop and support the implementation of policy and practice measures which will address structural issues that combine to trap households in energy poverty.

Through this work the project contributes to reducing participants' vulnerability to energy poverty, while at the same time cutting household energy consumption and associated GHG emissions.

For more information see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This document describes the structure and content of the EnergyMeasures web site, and outlines its future development.

Glossary

WP	Work Package
DoA	Description of Action
USX	User Experience
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
CMS	Content Management System
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
PNG	Portable Network Graphics

1 Introduction

1.1 Background / Deliverable Description

This deliverable reports on ongoing work associated with the EnergyMeasures website, which is now live and can be accessed at: <http://www.energymeasures.eu>.

Over the proceeding weeks and months, the website will be expanded upon through staged deployment of specific sections as content is generated from work carried out in other work packages. The objectives of the project website are defined and described in the EnergyMeasures Grant Agreement and Annex 1 (Description of Action).

As part of Work Package 6 (Communication, dissemination and exploitation), the website primarily serves the purpose of communicating the project contents to the outside world, *i.e.* to the general public. The agreement describes the task of website development as follows:

“- Development of a project website, which will include information about the objectives and work plan, upcoming events (seminars), published papers and awareness raising materials (target audience: all interested stakeholders, including: policy-makers, advocacy groups, householders, housings associations, NGOs, researchers, charities, etc.);
- Website section providing interactive step-by-step guidelines for developing a behaviour change strategy (target audience: peer groups providing support to energy poor householders).”

Oikoplus KG as lead partner of WP6 is responsible for the development, design and maintenance of the project website and will operate this channel as a communication platform for the entire duration of the project, *i.e.* regularly making available online the project results, informing on upcoming events and publishing news articles which are created together with the other project partners and edited by Oikoplus.

1.2 Relation to other EnergyMeasures deliverables

As the central channel for communicating the project content to the public and interested stakeholders, the website has links to all parts of the project and to all work packages. In a way, the website is the showcase of the project and creates transparency. The aim is to present the work of the EnergyMeasures consortium in a comprehensible way.

For this reason, individual work packages, including their deliverables and tasks as well as the project milestones, will be prepared and presented in a visually appealing and clear way. This should not only make the course of the project and its progress comprehensible to the interested public and stakeholders, but also serve as an orientation for the project partners themselves within the complex project structure, which will last several years.

2 Work done and current status

During the early project phase in September and October 2020 it became clear that the spread of the novel coronavirus SARS CoV-2 in Europe would require some changes to project's planning and implementation work. Consequently, the project kick-off meeting took place in virtual form only using the Microsoft Teams platform on September 17, 2020. The website remained technically unaffected by this development.

The web site was designed such that it could grow with the project as it progressed over its lifespan – both in terms of content and functionality. For instance, it is planned to replace some of the visualisations which are currently PNG graphics (*e.g.*, project milestones) with clickable HTML-5 elements or comparable web design elements in order to improve the user experience and significantly increase the multimedia capabilities of the website. These elements have been prepared conceptually and will be realised over the coming months.

2.1 Achieved objectives

The website is now functional, with the scope for further development in terms of technology and user interface design. Further steps will be taken over the coming weeks by Oikoplus KG in close cooperation with University College Cork – in accordance with the Grant Agreement and in line with ongoing work on the Communication Plan (D6.2) and the Dissemination Strategy (D.6.3) – that will be rolled out in parallel with work on those other WP6 tasks and completed by end of project month 3 (November 2020).

The website is structured into different sections:

- [a general front page](#) (see Screenshots 1-5)
- [an about page](#) with work plan descriptions (see Screenshots 8-11)
- [a partner site](#) (see Screenshot 12)
- [a news section](#) where project updates, narrative content and events will be published
- [a Media Center](#) where a range of material can be made accessible for stakeholders
- [a privacy policy page](#) (see Screenshot 13)

2.2 Methodology

WordPress was used to design the EnergyMeasures website. This widely used Content Management System (CMS) allows for a simple, modular design based on a wide variety of templates, which can be extended and modified by individual Cascading Style Sheets (CSS). Because of its greater flexibility, the WordPress theme Twenty Twenty was used for the design of the website.

The website can be continuously developed and changed over the course of the project. Especially with regards to the design of the website improvements are planned, which will enrich the user experience (UX). Over the long term, they should ensure an application-oriented, practical communication of the project topics, contents and results, combined with activating a Call-to-Action for behaviour change with regards to energy consumption patterns.

The widely used Search Engine Optimization (SEO) plugin YEOST was installed to improve the website's findability by search engines. In addition, the structure of the website and its individual pages have been SE-optimized, for example by using content-based permalinks for individual sub-pages.

The website asks its visitors for permission to use system relevant cookies. A privacy policy is stored. It can be accessed via a pop-up bar at the bottom of the front page.

The website is hosted on webspace of the commercial Austrian provider Easynome (easynome GmbH; Fernkorngasse 10/3/501; A-1100 Vienna; Austria). Oikoplus KG can look back on many years of positive experience with this company and has therefore decided to run the website on the company's servers as part of a web hosting package that already exists independently of EnergyMeasures.

2.3 Strategy

The website plays a central role in the communication and dissemination strategy of EnergyMeasures. It is the place where the contents of the project in any format (text, video, motion graphic, infographics, etc.), as well as the scientific and analytical results, are gathered and made downloadable.

The social media channels (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter) will link to the website repeatedly, as well as the other communication channels, e.g. press releases or articles in publications written by members of the EnergyMeasures consortium.

The project coordinator and Oikoplus KG will regularly ask the other project partners to provide content for the website, whether in the form of articles on ongoing project work for the news section of the website or in the form of photos and quotes, which provide human interest stories and sometimes insights into the working reality of the EnergyMeasures consortium. UCC will receive adequate training from Oikoplus KG in order to upload content to the news section of the website.

EnergyMeasures is a project that operates very closely to the lived experiences of European households. The project website is intended to reflect this, through content formats such as portraits, case studies, home stories, Q&As. The website should not only contain academic texts or technical descriptions of energy technology but should also provide insights into the more tangible aspects of the topic of energy poverty in order to raise awareness of this issue at a European level.

The website is particularly important for stakeholder involvement. Centrally placed Call-2-Actions are intended to encourage different stakeholders in the topic area of energy poverty to explore ways to change behaviour or to take measures that facilitate behavioural change in the use of energy.

For this purpose, interactive step-by-step guidelines for developing a behaviour change strategy are being developed. These guidelines will be placed on the website, probably in the context of a specially developed landing page, which will be integrated into the structure of the overall website, but will convey a clear key message, which does not require an overall understanding of the EnergyMeasures project. The requirement here is: low threshold.

3 Conclusions and perspective

The consortium partners in the EnergyMeasures project have the ambition to realise an excellent Horizon 2020 project over the duration of the project. This claim is to be represented and underlined by the website.

This requires the rapid and ongoing expansion of the existing website, which already offers all the possibilities of modern, digital project dissemination in all its functionality, but has not yet exhausted its potential in terms of user experience design.

In the coming weeks, Oikoplus KG will invest resources and project budget in the expansion and development of the website as the central communication channel of EnergyMeasures.

Screenshot 1: the EnergyMeasures homepage

Screenshot 2: abbreviated summary of Energy Measures project

Screenshot 3: Automatic user message website cookies

Screenshot 4: the website's privacy policy message

Screenshot 5: example of consortium partner feature

Screenshot 6: the website's menu

Screenshot 7: the website's menu, including submenu Work Plan

Screenshot 8: graphic outlining the project milestones

Screenshot 9: page listing links to each of the eight work packages

Screenshot 10: visual representation of deliverable outputs for WP2

Screenshot 11: landing page for WP7, includes title and lead partner

Screenshot 12: example of partners listed on the Partners page

Screenshot 13: EU flag and grant agreement details in page footer

